

Project ID N°: **101036449**

Call: **H2020-LC-GD-2020-3** box

Topic: **LC-GD-8-1-2020** - Innovative, systemic zero-pollution solutions to protect health, environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals

Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System

Start date of the project: **1st November 2021**

Duration: **42 months**

D6.11 - PROMISCES CEN Workshop Agreement

Main authors: **Millaray Sierra Olea (DECHEMA), Aleksandra Jurewicz (DECHEMA)**

Lead Beneficiary: **DECHEMA**

Type of delivery: **R**

Dissemination Level: **PU**

Filename and version: **PROMISCES_D6-11_CEN-Workshop-Agreement (version 1)**

Website: **www.promisces.eu**

Due date: April 30th, 2025

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N°101036449

© European Union, 2025

No third-party textual or artistic material included on the publication without the copyright holder's prior consent to further dissemination by other third parties.

Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged

Disclaimer

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Document History

This document has been through the following revisions:

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer	Description
0.1	20/03/2025	Millaray Sierra Olea (DECHEMA) Aleksandra Jurewicz (DECHEMA)	Working document
0.2	02/04/2025	Nicole Heine (DECHEMA)	WPL revision
0.3	02/04/2025	Floriane Sermondadaz (IEIC)	Quality control
1.0	03/04/2025	Julie Lions (BRGM)	Final version for submission

Authorisation

Authorisation	Name	Status	Date
Review & Validation	Nicole Heine	WP6 leader	02/04/2025
Quality Control	Floriane Sermondadaz	Administrative and financial manager	02/04/2025
Approval	J. Lions	Project coordinator	02/04/2025

Distribution

This document has been distributed to:

Name	Title	Version issued	Date of issue
All partners	Project Consortium	Version 1	03/04/2025

Executive Summary

This deliverable D6.11 presents insights into the development and the outcome of the CEN (European Committee for Standardization) Workshop Agreement (CWA) on “Soil-sediment-water system – Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances”. Developed collaboratively with PROMISCES and the ZeroPM and SCENARIOS sister projects, the CWA addresses challenges related to persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic (PM(T)) and very persistent, very mobile (vPvM) substances, including PFAS, in soil, sediment and water systems.

The primary goals of the D6.11 CWA are to address challenges related to the management of PM(T) substances across environmental compartments. These challenges are addressed in the CWA by offering solutions from the three Horizon Europe funded projects in the categories of prevention, substitution, monitoring, remediation, risk governance of remediation projects, and hazard and exposure assessments.

Key solutions include new methods for PFAS analysis, risk assessment improvements, and solutions for PFAS removal from various matrices like wastewater, sediment, and sludge. The CWA aims to promote a European circular economy and focuses on five specific routes: semi-closed water cycles for drinking water supply, wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation, nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for fertilisers, material recovery from dredged sediment for eco-materials, and groundwater and soil remediation. The information contained in the CWA is relevant to actors along the various circular economy and PM(T) exposure routes, including researchers, public authorities, water utilities, and solution-developing companies.

List of Acronyms

BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CWA	CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V.
DSF	Decision Support Framework
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gemeinnützige GmbH
NGI	Norwegian Geotechnical Institute
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PM(T)	Persistent, Mobile, and Potentially Toxic
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
TZW	DVGW-Technologiezentrum Wasser
vPvM	(very) Persistent and (very) Mobile

1 What is a CWA?

A CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA) serves as a collaborative, consensus-based document developed within the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) framework. CWAs play an essential role in tackling emerging challenges by establishing structured approaches before formal standards are introduced. They document project findings and solutions in a standardised and easily understandable manner, providing a structured overview and a common language for conveying technical information to various end-users.

As a publicly accessible document, the CWA enables the widespread dissemination of the developed approaches and solutions, fostering their adoption by individuals and organisations facing similar challenges.

2 Topic of the PROMISCES CWA

As part of the PROMISCES project, a CWA was developed to consolidate strategies, best practices, and innovative solutions to manage (very) persistent, (very) mobile, and potentially toxic (PM(T)/vPvM) substances in the soil-sediment-water system. These substances, such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), pose significant environmental and health risks, making their effective management a priority for policymakers, regulators, researchers, water utilities and industry stakeholders. The PROMISCES CWA outlines solutions and alternative approaches for prevention, substitution, remediation, co-creation and the prioritization, monitoring, and hazard and exposure assessment of PM(T) substances. Special attention was given to five circular economy routes by aligning developed solutions to specific routes: semi-closed water cycles for drinking water supply, wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation, nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for fertilisers, material recovery from dredged sediment for eco-materials, and groundwater and soil remediation.

The PROMISCES CWA, titled “Soil-sediment-water system – Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances”, provides practical guidance for areas where flexibility and rapid development are needed. It also serves as a reference for exploitation activities, providing a foundation for future work, standard development, or guideline creation related to managing PMT/vPvM substances. With a validity of three years, the CWA ensures that project outcomes not only provide immediate benefits but also maintain long-term relevance and applicability.

3 The CWA process

The CWA process started in October 2023 with a submission of the [PROMISCES CEN Workshop Business Plan](#)¹, which laid out the initial foundation for the chosen topic. The topic was finalized during the CEN Workshop on 15 February 2024, which was open to all interested parties, encouraging contributions from decision-makers, academics, municipal and industrial actors, and civil society both within and beyond Europe. Additionally, two sister projects, ZeroPM and SCENARIOS, participated in the workshop, presenting their aims and concerns, and contributing to the draft process. Contributions

¹ Bagheri L. (2023). Deliverable D6.10 – PROMISCES CEN Workshop Business Plan.
<https://zenodo.org/records/15118284>

were also made by the European project ARAGORN. From February 2024 onwards, stakeholders participated in five online meetings, with the final one occurring in January 2025.

Leadership roles for the CWA were confirmed, with Dr. Thomas Track (DECHEMA) as Chair, Dr. Veronika Zhiteneva (KWB) as Vice-Chair, and Dr. Madlen Schmutde (DIN) as Secretary. Participating members identified their areas of interest through an online survey, forming dedicated teams led by experts: Prevention/Substitution (Sarah Hale; TZW), Measures/Remediation (Veronika Zhiteneva; KWB), Prioritisation and co-creation (Hans Peter Arp; NGI), Monitoring (Anne Togola; BRGM), and Risk Assessment (Martine Bakker; RIVM). All PROMISCES contributors are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of the involved PROMISCES partners and sister projects.

Person	Partner/Project
Thomas Track, Aleksandra Jurewicz, Millaray Sierra Olea	DECHEMA/PROMISCES
Alessandro Frugis, Marco Lazzazzara	ACEA/PROMISCES
Peter Behnisch	BDS/PROMISCES
Julie Lions, Amélie Cavelan, Anne Togola, Stéfan Colombano	BRGM/PROMISCES
Zsuzsanna Nagy-Kovács	BWW/PROMISCES
Sandra Valero González	CBT/PROMISCES
Carme Bosch	EURECAT/PROMISCES
Eric van Hullebusch	IPGP/PROMISCES
Miren López de Alda	IDAEA-CISIC/PROMISCES
Veronika Zhiteneva, Ulf Miehe, Pia Schumann, Sonja Sterling, Yuki Bartels	KWB/PROMISCES
Sarah Hale	TZW/ZeroPM
Mihaela Mirea	LOMARTOV/SCENARIOS
Martine Bakker	RIVM/PROMISCES
Maria Grazia Ascì, Paolo Crocetti	SIMAM/PROMISCES
Evgenia Benova, Yana Topalova	UNISOFIA/PROMISCES
Thomas James Oudega	TUWien/PROMISCES
Jochen Kuckelkorn	UBA/PROMISCES
Ali Hydar, Francesco Fatone, Massimiliano Sgroi	UNIVPM/PROMISCES

By April 2024, all registered participants (45) were granted access to DECHEMA's SharePoint folder for collaborative work on the document. At least 14 of the participants are external to the PROMISCES project, fulfilling project KPI 6.4 "Number of project external stakeholders included in the CEN workshop agreement for the co-creation of the DSF" as described in the project Description of Action with a target: 5-15.

The CWA meetings concluded with a final session on 29 January 2025, marking the end of the collaborative drafting phase with participants. Following final revisions coordinated by DIN, the completed CWA was published on the official CEN-CENELEC website in April 2025 and will be publicly available online for three years. Participants are encouraged to promote the document within their networks, and PROMISCES will actively disseminate the publication through its communication channels.

This deliverable presents the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) titled "Soil-sediment-water system - Solutions to deal with PMT/vPvM substances". It is a key output of the PROMISCES project, developed to support its communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts.

The CWA document is available at the following link: [cwa18201_2025.pdf](#).